

Health Insurance Literacy assessment tools: A systematic review protocol

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Abstract

Introduction: Health Insurance Literacy (HIL) is a concept that has gained growing attention in the last few years. Despite its increasing popularity, most of the research conducted around HIL has taken place in the United States. At the same time, there is still a lack of consistency in its conceptualization and instruments used to assess it.

Objectives: This systematic review aims to (1) describe measures used to assess HIL and related constructs, (2) identify validated measures used to assess HIL and related constructs, and (3) assess the development of the found validated measures as well as their methodological quality and measurement properties.

Methods: A systematic review will be conducted using ERIC, Econlit, PubMed, PsycInfo, CINAHL and Google Scholar bibliographic databases along with an environmental scan and reference-harvesting. Search strategy will be consulted with a librarian and peer reviewed. Two reviewers will screen titles and abstracts as well as full texts against the inclusion criteria and complete data extraction. Results will be summarized and synthesized following PRISMA and COSMIN guidelines and recommendations.

Results/Discussion: The results of this review will inform the construction of a framework for HIL as well as of validated measurement instruments with the aim of facilitating and consolidating research around the topic.

Introduction

Being able to make good decisions regarding a complex product such as health insurance requires certain skills and knowledge. The sum of these skills and knowledge has been addressed as Health Insurance Literacy (HIL), a term that has gained increasing attention over the last decade. In 2011, a roundtable sponsored by Consumers Union and held at the Kaiser Family Foundation in Washington, DC (US), which included a variety of experts from academia, consumer advocacy groups, health insurance, and private research firms; developed a first definition for HIL: “the degree to which individuals have the knowledge, ability, and confidence to find and evaluate information about health plans, select the best plan for their own (or their family’s) financial and health circumstances, and use the plan once enrolled” (Consumers Union, 2012).

In 2013, a literature review on HIL summarized relevant findings on topics such as financial literacy, health literacy as well as HIL and consumer decision-making. The review concluded that even though there was no standardized measure for HIL, there is evidence that consumers are not aware of how to obtain and process information to select an optimal health insurance plan based on their circumstances; and called for the development of a standardized measure for HIL. (Kim et al., 2013)

In 2014, a group of researchers synthesized information gathered from the previously mentioned roundtable, a literature review on consumers’ understanding of health insurance, key informant interviews and stakeholder meetings to construct a conceptual model for HIL (Paez et al., 2014).

Even though there have been some important developments around the concept of HIL, overall research is still in its infant shoes. Most of the research so far has taken place in the US and is based on the US health

insurance system. Further, conceptualizations oftentimes seem inexplicit with overall limited information on how HIL was eventually assessed.

Objectives

1. To describe measures used to assess HIL and related constructs, such as knowledge and understanding of, or familiarity with health insurance;
2. To identify validated measures that aim at assessing HIL and related constructs;
3. To assess development of validated measures found, their methodological quality and quality of measurement properties.

Methods

Searches

A systematic review of the existing literature in economics, consumer behavior as well as communication sciences and related fields will be conducted. The search strategy will be consulted with a librarian and a Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategy (PRESS)(McGowan et al., 2016) will be done consequently.

The following databases will be searched:

- ERIC
- Econlit
- PubMed
- PsycInfo
- CINAHL
- Google Scholar

The search will be complemented with an environmental scan and reference-harvesting to identify relevant studies that could have been missed by the database search.

Types of studies to be included

Studies that describe or utilize quantitative or mixed methods measures that aim at assessing HIL and related constructs.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The search will not be restricted to any geographic location or population, nor to a specific time frame. However, only studies in English will be included.

Studies that describe or utilize purely qualitative measures for HIL and related constructs, such as semi-structured interviews and focus groups will be excluded.

Condition or domain being studied

In 2011 the term “Health Insurance Literacy” was defined by a roundtable of experts as “the degree to which individuals have the knowledge, ability, and confidence to find and evaluate information about health plans, select the best plan for their own (or their family’s) financial and health circumstances, and use the plan once enrolled”.

Given that this definition and conceptual model for HIL (Paez et al., 2014) are relatively young, and specific to the US; the scope of the search and review will be broadened to cover related constructs such

as health insurance knowledge, familiarity, understanding, and comprehension. The purpose of this is to include relevant instruments attempting to assess the different domains included in Paez et al.'s conceptual model prior to the definition and conceptualization of HIL in the US, as well as attempts to measure HIL and related constructs in diverse cultural contexts, particularly outside the US.

Participants/population

General. Any target population, including proxies or respondents, who provide answers about other subjects or on their behalf.

Main outcome(s)

- Identification of validated measures for HIL and related constructs.
- Critical appraisal of measurement development, methodological quality and measurement properties for found validated measures for HIL.

Additional outcomes

- Summary of found validated and non-validated measures used to assess HIL and related constructs.
- Domains assessed by measures according to the HIL conceptual model by Paez et al. (2014)
- Type of measure (self-reported vs. objective)
- Number of items
- Additional information on measures, such as: country, year, and whether the measure was specifically developed for the study in question or has been previously developed

Data extraction (selection and coding)

Title and abstract screening, full text screening, as well as data extraction will be completed by two independent reviewers. Potential discrepancies between reviewers will be discussed in order to be resolved. In case no consensus is reached, a third independent reviewer will be consulted in order to make a final decision.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

Risk of bias and quality assessment will be conducted as part of the data extraction and assessed by two independent reviewers according to the criteria specified by the COSMIN checklists (Mokkink et al., 2016).

Strategy for data synthesis

Search results will be synthesized and reported in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (Moher et al., 2015). General information and data on found measures will be summarized. Further analysis and data synthesis will be carried out for found validated measures. For validated measures, information on quality of instrument development, methodological quality of measurement properties and quality of measurement properties will be summarized according to the COSMIN guidelines and recommendations (Terwee et al., 2018). Additional information, such as country, target population, language, assessment method (self-reported/subjective or objective), domains assessed, and number of items will be summarized and presented.

Discussion

The results of this systematic review will contribute to the still emerging field of research on HIL. Providing a summary of available measures on HIL and related constructs will help researchers to develop more specific frameworks on HIL and to eventually create culturally or setting specific measures to assess HIL.

From a research perspective, including measures on HIL in studies on health and related behaviors, as well as healthcare utilization, may shed light on the contribution of literacy, and potentially numeracy, on these outcomes and highlight potential ramifications of low HIL in individuals and groups that may lack sufficient skills. Further, it may inform the development of interventions addressing suboptimal health insurance choices or usage thereof.

From a policy perspective, understanding the distribution of HIL among the general population may provide evidence on the equal or unequal distribution of access to healthcare and demand thereof. It, thus, could inform policy makers' discussions on the accessibility of health insurance systems from an individual's perspective and to provide information on how to facilitate health insurance decision-making and its usage, potentially improving individual and population welfare.

Additional information

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Conflicts of interest: None known

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